

Research Article

Evaluation of Subsoil Corrosivity Condition around a Sewage Pond using the Electrical Resistivity Method. A Case Study from the Basement Complex Terrain of Ile-Ife, Southwestern Nigeria

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Abstract

Evaluation of subsoil corrosivity using the electrical resistivity method was carried out around a sewage pond in the Basement Complex terrain of Ile-Ife, Southwestern Nigeria with the aim of determining the subsoil geoelectric parameters (apparent resistivities) around the sewage pond at depth range of 0.5 m, 1.5 m and 3.0 m and to categorize the area into different corrosivity zones. The depths of investigation were selected based on the theoretical relationship ($Z = 0.125AB$) between depth of investigation Z (m) and the current electrode spacing (AB (m)) for Schlumberger Array. Twenty-five Vertical Electrical Sounding (VES) stations were occupied with ABEM SAS 1000 terrameter along five N-S trending with maximum of 200 m long geophysical traverses. The station-station interval of 40 m was used to acquire apparent resistivities for electrode spacing ($AB/2$) of 2 m, 6 m and 12 m respectively which correspond to the selected depths theoretically; iso - resistivity maps were generated using Surfer 8 Software for each depth. The maps were qualitatively interpreted while three main subsoil corrosivity zones were delineated around the sewage pond. At depth 0.5 m, the western zone of the pond is underlain by slightly corrosive subsoil while other part is underlain by practically non-corrosive subsoil. At depth 1.5 m, the western part is characterized by both moderately corrosive subsoil and slightly corrosive subsoil while other part is characterized by practically non-corrosive subsoil. At 3.0 m depth, similar subsoil effect was observed. It can be concluded that the area around the sewage pond is underlain by moderately corrosive, slightly corrosive and practically non-corrosive subsoil. However, the degree of corrosivity around the pond increases westward with depth.

Key Words: Electrical Resistivity, Subsoil, Corrosivity, Sewage Pond, Ile-Ife, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

For design and corrosion risk assessment purposes, it is desirable to estimate the corrosivity/aggressivity of soils (<http://www.corrosion-doctors.org/CP/soil-resist.htm>). Knowledge of soil corrosivity is critical for the effective design of cathodic protection measures, or predicting the lifetime of a buried steel structure.

Factors such as soil composition, moisture content, pore water chemistry and pH (hydrogen potency) control the ground resistivity, which is the main diagnostic factor. Soil resistivity is a measure of soil's ability to retard the conduction of an electric current. Its resistivity parameter is very widely used in practice and generally considered to be the dominant variable in the absence of microbial activity (Baeckman and Schwenk, 1975, Fontana and Green, 1978, Aguloye, 1984, Olorunfemi and Ojo, 1994, Adesida, et al., 2002, Idornigie, et al., 2006).

The electrical resistivity method is highly significant in cases of in-situ determination of the degree of corrosiveness of soils. Sandy soils are high up on the resistivity scale and therefore considered the least corrosive. Clay soils, especially those contaminated with saline water are on the opposite end of the spectrum (<http://www.corrosion-doctors.org/CP/soil-resist.htm>).

The study area is the sewage disposal site of the Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Southwestern Nigeria. It lies within $7^{\circ}30.46'$ - $7^{\circ}30.34'$ N Latitude and $4^{\circ}30.76'$ - $4^{\circ}30.68'$ E Longitude (Fig. 1).

The area is underlain by Mica Schist and Grey Gneiss which falls within the Basement Complex terrain of Nigeria (Rahaman, 1989). Its vegetation is located within a tropical rainforest belt of Nigeria. However, this rainforest vegetation has been reduced to a derived savannah type of vegetation as a result of human activities such as intensive land cultivation, bush burning, land clearing for agricultural and construction purposes.

Figure 1: The Base Map of the Study Area.

The area is characterised by alternation of two distinct seasons: the rainy season and the dry season. The rainy season lasts for seven months (April to October) with mean annual rainfall of 1500mm-2000mm while the dry season begins in November and ends in March. The diurnal range in temperature is not significant, but the daily temperature can reach 29 °C and is seldom lower than 25 °C.

The area was investigated for corrosive soils and degree of corrosivity in order to be able to predict areas of potential problems further to future engineering construction around the sewage site.

METHOD OF STUDY

The electrical resistivity method involving the vertical electrical sounding (VES) was used for the investigation. In this method, artificially generated direct current or low frequency alternating current was injected into the ground via two current electrodes while the resulting potential difference is measured by another pair of potential electrodes in the vicinity of the current flow (e.g Adepelumi, et al., 2001; Adewumi and Olorunfemi, 2005). The Schlumberger Array (Fig. 2) was adopted for (1) that fewer movement of the electrodes are needed, (2) lateral variations cause greater errors when potential electrodes are moved than when the current electrodes are moved, (3) the duplication of readings with the same values of half current electrode spacing (AB/2) but different values of potential electrode spacing (MN/2) also allows an approximate correction to be made for the effects of lateral variation.

Figure 2: The Schlumberger Electrode Configuration.

Twenty five (25) VES stations were occupied on five (5), N-S spanned, 200 m long geophysical traverses established around the sewage pond using the ABEM terrameter Signal Averaging System 1000 Series resistivity meter to obtain the apparent resistivity. The VES inter station interval was 40 m. Electrode separation ($AB/2$) of 2 m, 6 m and 12 m which is equivalent to depth of investigation 0.5 m, 1.5 m and 3 m were adopted based on the theoretical relationship ($Z = 0.125AB$) between depth of investigation Z (m) and the current electrode spacing (AB) for Schlumberger Array. Apparent resistivity distribution with the subsoil condition beneath each traverse was produced. The iso-resistivity map of the area was generated using the Surfer 8 software for depth range of 0.5 m, 1.5 m and 3.0 m respectively. The area was categorized into different soil corrosivity zones using the resistivity classification scale: $\leq 10 \Omega\text{m}$ – Very Strongly Corrosive (VSC); $10 - 30 \Omega\text{m}$ – Very Corrosive (VC); $30 - 60 \Omega\text{m}$ - Moderately Corrosive (MC); $60 - 180 \Omega\text{m}$ – Slightly Corrosive (SC) and above $180 \Omega\text{m}$ – Practically Non-Corrosive (PNC) modified after Baeckman and Schwenk, (1975), Agunloye, (1984) and British Standard BS, (1377).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Isoresistivity Maps

Subsoil Condition at 0.5 metre Depth

The resistivity values obtained for each of the twenty-five VES stations at 0.5 m depth are as presented in the iso resistivity contour map in Fig. 3. VES stations 16, 17, 21 and 24 at the west and north-western parts of the pond are characterized by resistivity values between $60 \Omega\text{m}$ and $180 \Omega\text{m}$. These zones are probably underlain by slightly corrosive subsoil. Other parts around the pond have resistivity values greater than $180 \Omega\text{m}$. The area is probably underlain by practically non corrosive subsoil.

Subsoil Condition at 1.5 meter Depth

Fig. 4 presents the iso-apparent resistivity map at the depth. Moderately corrosive subsoil was observed at the western part of the waste pond beneath VES stations 23 and 25 respectively. The resistivity values range between $30 \Omega\text{m}$ and $60 \Omega\text{m}$. VES stations 11, 16, 17, 19, 20, 21, 22, and 24 cover the western part of the waste pond. The apparent resistivity value of the area ranges between $60 \Omega\text{m}$ and $180 \Omega\text{m}$, hence, it is suspected that the area is underlain by slightly corrosive subsoil. At the eastern part of the waste pond, the resistivity value greater than $180 \Omega\text{m}$ were obtained. This indicates that traverses 1, 2, 3 and part of traverse 4 are probably underlain by practically non corrosive subsoil.

Subsoil Conditions at 3.0 meter Depth

The resistivity values beneath the twenty – five VES stations are presented in the Iso resistivity map in Fig. 5. VES stations 17, 19, 21, 23 and 25 are probably underlain by moderately corrosive subsoil. The stations are closer to the waste pond. These VES stations have resistivity value range between $30 \Omega\text{m}$ and $60 \Omega\text{m}$. It is possible that the area is underlain by clay or contains leachate plume. The western and the central portion of the map are probably characterized by slightly corrosive subsoil. VES stations 9, 11, 16, 20, 22 and 24 fall within the area. The resistivity value range of between $60 \Omega\text{m}$ and $180 \Omega\text{m}$ are delineated around the environment. However, the subsoil around the eastern part of the waste pond probably is practically non-corrosive. This is evident from the resistivity values of greater than $180 \Omega\text{m}$ which were observed in the area.

Figure 3: Iso-Apparent Resistivity Map of Subsoil (AB/2 = 2 m); Depth Z (0.5 m)).

Figure 4: Iso-Apparent Resistivity Map of Subsoil (AB/2 = 6 m); Depth Z (1.5 m)).

Figure 5: Iso- Apparent Resistivity Map of Subsoil (AB/2 = 12 m); Depth Z (3.0 m)).

CONCLUSION

A subsoil corrosivity evaluation has been carried out around a sewage pond situated within Ile-Ife, Southwestern Nigeria using the electrical resistivity method. The qualitative interpretation of the iso-apparent resistivity contour map has provided adequate information regarding the degree of corrosivity of the subsoil in the study area. The subsoil condition around the sewage pond were categorized as slightly corrosive, moderately corrosive and practically non-corrosive based on apparent resistivity range of 30-60 Ω m, 60-180 Ω m and greater than 180 Ω m respectively at depths of 0.5 m, 1.5 m and 3.0 m. The western flank of the pond is characterized by both slightly corrosive and moderately corrosive subsoil with resistivity value range between 30 and 180 Ω m. This probably indicates the presence of clay or infiltration of leachate plumes. However, the degree of corrosivity increases with depth. The eastern part with resistivity value greater than 180 Ω m is characterized by practically non corrosive subsoil suggesting westward flow of groundwater/leachate in the area. It can be concluded that sub soil corrosivity around the study area increases westward with depth.

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